

Poly-Vanadates of Less Common Metals - Electrometric Investigations on the Composition of Zirconium Poly-Vanadates as a Function of pH.

R. S. Saxena and M. C. Jain

The formation and composition of Zirconium poly-vanadates, obtained by the interaction of Zirconium sulphate and different alkali vanadates (ortho, pyro and meta) have been studied by means of glass electrode titrations between the reactants at different pH levels. The sharp inflections in titration curves provide cogent evidence for the formation of zirconium ortho-($3\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$), pyro-($\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$) and meta ($\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$), vanadates at pH ranges (5.8—7.5), (4.0—5.5) and (3.0—4.0) respectively. The precipitation of zirconium pyro-vanadate has been found to be quantitative and the titrations offer a simple, rapid and accurate method for the determination of zirconium in solution at suitable concentrations and pH ranges.

Vanadium (V) oxy-anions, which figure prominently in discussions of isopoly acids, exist in solution as four different stable species¹⁻³, viz. (VO_4^{3-}), ($\text{V}_2\text{O}_7^{4-}$), (VO_3^{3-}) and ($\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{27}^{4-}$) in the vicinity of pH, 12.0, 10.0, 7.0 and 4.5 respectively. The investigations on the reactions of these anions with heavy metal salts at different pH levels have been the subject of considerable interest in authors' laboratories due to their peculiar behaviour and have yielded significant results on poly vanadates of several metals⁴⁻⁸. The literature on vanadates of zirconium is very scanty. A few old references are, however, available regarding the preliminary preparative studies of zirconium vanadates of uncertain compositions. Tanatar and Kurowsky⁹ obtained zirconium oxy-chlorovanadate $m.\text{ZrCl}_4 \cdot n.\text{Zr}_3(\text{VO}_4)_4 \cdot p.\text{ZrO}_2$ by mixing alkali vanadate and ZrCl_4 . G. Peyronel¹⁰ reported the formation of Zirconyl Vanadate. $3\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 2\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by heating NH_4VO_3 and $\text{ZrO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. A Burdese and M. Barlvro¹¹ studied the binary system $\text{ZrO}_2\text{-V}_2\text{O}_5$ and reported the formation of ZrV_2O_7 . In view of the conflicting reports of earlier workers, it was considered of interest to study the formation and composition of zirconium vanadates, obtained by the interaction of zirconium sulphate and alkali vanadates at different H^+ ion concentration, which plays an important role in the precipitation of metal vanadates, by means of glass electrode titrations.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Anal. R. (B.D.H.) reagents, V_2O_5 , NaOH, Zirconium sulphate and reagent grade HCl were used and their solutions prepared in air free conductivity water. Zirconium in Zirconium sulphate solution was estimated as its pyro-phosphate^{1,2} (ZrP_2O_7).

A standard solution of sodium orthovanadate was prepared by digesting one mole of V_2O_5 in boiling solution of NaOH containing six moles of it. The alkali pyro and meta vanadate solutions were obtained by adding two and four moles of HCl respectively to a solution containing one mole of orthovanadate at 100°.

pH measurements were carried out on a Cambridge null deflection type pH meter. A glass electrode of the range 0-13pH was used in conjunction with S.C.E. The observed values of pH were plotted against the titrant added and from the sharp inflection in titration curves and maximum value of dpH/dv , the end points were determined. Fig. 1 and 2 represent the direct and reverse titration curves and the results are summarised in table-I.

Fig. 1. Direct pH titrations between zirconium sulphate and sodium vanadates.
 Curve-I. ml of M/10 $Zr(SO_4)_2$, added to 25 ml. of M/100 $3Na_2O.V_2O_5$.
 Curve-II. ml. of M/20 $Zr(SO_4)_2$, added to 2.5ml. of M/125 $2Na_2O.V_2O_5$.
 Curve-III. ml. of M/10 $Zr(SO_4)_2$, added to 30 ml. of M/50 $Na_2O.V_2O_5$.

Fig. 2. Reverse pH titrations between zirconium sulphate and sodium vanadates.
 Curve-I. ml. of M/10 $3Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 25 ml. of M/50 $Zr(SO_4)_2$.
 Curve-II. ml. of M/10 $2Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 25 ml. of M/50 $Zr(SO_4)_2$.
 Curve-III. ml. of M/10 $Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 30 ml. of M/100 $Zr(SO_4)_2$.

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TABLE I

Summary of the results of Glass electrode titrations.

Molarity of Solutions.		Equivalence points (ml).			Formula supported.
		Calc.	Obs.		
3 Na ₂ O. V ₂ O ₅ Zr(SO ₄) ₂		<i>Ortho-vanadate titrations.</i>			
Direct titrations, Fig. 1. Curve I.					
M/100	M/10	3.75	1.8	3.7	3(ZrO ₂ .2Na ₂ O).4V ₂ O ₅ and (3ZrO ₂ .2V ₂ O ₅)
M/200	M/25	4.7	2.4	4.7	
M/500	M/40	3.0	1.50	3.0	
M/750	M/50	4.0	2.00	4.05	
Reverse titrations, Fig. 2. Curve I.					
M/10	M/50	3.33		3.35	(3ZrO ₂ .2V ₂ O ₅)
M/15	M/80	3.12		3.10	
M/25	M/100	4.17		4.15	
M/60	M/200	5.0		5.0	
2Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ Zr(SO ₄) ₂		<i>Pyro vanadate titrations.</i>			
Direct titrations, Fig. 1. Curve II.					
M/50	M/10	5.0		5.0	(ZrO ₂ .V ₂ O ₅)
M/125	M/20	4.0		4.0	
M/250	M/30	3.0		3.0	
M/400	M/40	2.5		2.45	
Reverse titrations, Fig. 2. Curve II.					
M/10	M/50	5.0		5.0	(ZrO ₂ .V ₂ O ₅)
M/15	M/100	3.75		3.75	
M/20	M/150	3.33		3.35	
Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ Zr(SO ₄) ₂		<i>Meta-vanadate titrations.</i>			
Direct titrations, Fig. 1. Curve III.					
M/50	M/10	3.0		2.95	(ZrO ₂ .2V ₂ O ₅)
M/100	M/25	3.75		3.70	
M/300	M/50	2.5		2.5	
M/500	M/100	3.0		3.0	
Reverse titrations, Fig. 2. Curve III.					
M/10	M/100	6.0		6.0	(ZrO ₂ .2V ₂ O ₅)
M/10	M/150	4.0		4.0	
M/15	M/200	4.5		4.55	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Saxena and co-workers¹⁻³ have shown that the addition of acid to alkali ortho-vanadate and NaOH to V₂O₅ solutions at room temperature causes the formation of various polyanions of uncertain composition, but when the solutions were heated after each addition of titrant, three different vanadates, pyro-(2Na₂O.V₂O₅), meta-(Na₂O.V₂O₅) and poly-(Na₂O.2.5V₂O₅) are formed. Hence it was considered of importance to ascertain whether similar salts of heavy metals may be precipitated as a result of double decomposition. The reaction between alkali vanadates and zirconium (IV) has therefore been studied by glass electrode titration technique.

Ortho-vanadate Titrations : The pH of $Zr(SO_4)_2$ and $3Na_2O.V_2O_5$ solutions were measured and found to be in the vicinity of 2.0 and 12.0 respectively. Figs 1 and 2 illustrate the changes occurring in H^+ ion concentrations during the reaction between Zr^{4+} and VO_4^{3-} ions. In the case of direct titrations (fig. 1- curve.I) when zirconium salt from the microburette is added to ortho-vanadate in the titration cell, pH of the solution gradually decreases ; on the addition of 0.75 mcle of $Zr(SO_4)_2$ per mole of ortho-vanadate. a sharp fall in pH is noted, indicating the interaction of reactants in the ratio of $ZrO_2 : V_2O_5 :: 3 : 4$ corresponding to the formation of $3(ZrO_2 : 2Na_2O).4V_2O_5$ as an intermediate species in the pH range (9-9.5). On further addition of $Zr(SO_4)_2$, a second more pronounced inflection is obtained at the ratio $ZrO_2 : V_2O_5 :: 3 : 2$ as a consequence of the conversion of intermediate specie into final compound Zirconium ortho-vanadate ($3ZrO_2.2V_2O_5$). In the case of reverse titrations (fig. 2-curve-I), when ortho-vanadate was used as titrant, only one inflection is noted corresponding to the formation of Zirconium ortho-vanadate ($3ZrO_2.2V_2O_5$).

From the preceding study it may be concluded that, when alkali ortho-vanadate is present in excess, precipitation of zirconium ortho-vanadate proceeds through the formation of an intermediate specie, which with the increase in Zr^{4+} contents changes into the ortho-vanadate. The reaction equilibria can be stated as follows.

Pyro-vanadate Titrations : Alkali pyro-vanadate solution was prepared as described earlier (pH ≈ 10). The plots of pH values, (obtained on the addition of Zirconium salt to pyro-vanadate soln.) Vs. the volume of each aliquot, are regular in form and exhibit well defined break at the point corresponding to the formation of zirconium pyro-vanadate ($ZrO_2.V_2O_5$). Reverse titration curves (fig. 2-curve II) are also regular in form and show a sharp upward jump at the end point, corresponding to the reacting ratio of $ZrO_2 : V_2O_5$ as 1 : 1, and confirming the formation of zirconium pyro-vanadate. The reaction taking place can be represented as follows :

Meta-vanadate Titrations : Sodium meta-vanadate solution was prepared by the addition of 4 moles of HCl per mole of ortho-vanadate at 100° and its reaction with zirconium (IV) has been investigated as before by performing both direct and reverse glass electrode titrations, with each of the reactants alternately used as titrant. Direct as well as reverse pH titration curves yield well defined breaks and indicate the interaction of Zr^{4+} and meta-vanadate in the ratio of 1 : 2 and the formation of zirconium-meta vanadate ($ZrO_2.2V_2O_5$) in the pH range (3.0-4.0)

In these titrations the addition of alcohol does not appreciably change the end point or the nature of the curves, but the magnitude of the jump in pH increases in its presence. Glass electrode titration curves are regular in shape, dpH/dv is strongly marked at the end point and the results are accurate and reproducible (Table-I).

The present investigation confirms the formation and precipitation of zirconium ortho, pyro and meta vanadates at pH ranges (5.8-7.5), (4.0-5.5) and (3.0-4.0) respectively.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
MALAVIYA REGIONAL ENGINEERING COLLEGE,
JAIPUR.

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